

GAIA mean astrometric precision versus V magnitude

L Lindegren 1998 Sept 27
SAG-LL-023

The mean astrometric precision of GAIA is computed as function of V magnitude and sky position taking into account

1. the general variation of the sky-averaged precision with G magnitude
2. the distribution of V-I colour indices for given V and sky position, using a simple galactic model (same as in SAG-LL-012)
3. the variation of astrometric precision with ecliptic latitude

From the galactic model, the mean V-I and mean G magnitude were computed for given V and a number of directions in galactic coordinates. For the transformation G(V, V-I), Equation (4) in SAG-LL-017 was used. This mean G was then converted to the sky-averaged parallax precision (se_par_sky) by means of the formula:

```
x = 10.0**(0.4*(G-15.0))
se_par_sky = sqrt(8.0 + 190.0*x + 7.0*x**2 + 1e-8*x**6)
se_par_sky = amax1(se_par_sky, 4.0)
```

which is an analytical fit to the mean unreddened data in Table 5 of SAG-LL-017. The sky-averaged precision in proper motion was taken as

```
se_pm_sky = 0.7 * se_par_sky
```

where the factor 0.7 is for a temporal baseline of about 4.5 years. The variation with ecliptic latitude (eclat), for revolving angle xi = 55 deg, was computed as follows:

```
abslat = abs(eclat)
IF (abslat .LT. 35.0) THEN
  x = (abslat/35.0)**2
  f_par = 1.143 - 0.105*x - 0.059*x**2
  f_pm = 1.089 - 0.091*x - 0.175*x**2
ELSE
  x = ((90.0 - abslat)/55.0)**2
  f_par = 0.795 + 0.086*x + 0.098*x**2
  f_pm = 1.079 - 0.204*x - 0.052*x**2
ENDIF
se_par = f_par * se_par_sky
se_pm = f_pm * se_pm_sky
```

The resulting se_pm refers to the mean of the two coordinates (eclat, eclon) or (glat, glon).

Results are given in three tables:

Table 1: Sky averages

Table 2: Zonal averages (averaged over galactic longitude)

Table 3: Local averages (averaged in colour for a number of galactic directions)

All tables use the same format, with the following 10 columns:

V	= V magnitude
glat	= galactic latitude in degrees (set to 0 in Table 1)
glon	= galactic longitude in degrees (set to 0 in Table 1 and 2)
eclat	= mean ecliptic latitude in degrees (set to 0 in Table 1)
area	= area of sky in deg**2 assigned to the direction

dens = mean density of stars (stars per deg**2 per mag)
 <V-I> = mean colour index
 <G> = mean G magnitude
 <se_par> = mean standard error in parallax (microarcsec)
 <se_pm> = mean standard error in proper motion (microarcsec/yr)

Table 1 and 2 are given hereafter. Because of its size, the whole of Table 3 is not included, but is provided as a separate ASCII file (sag_ll_023_tab3.txt).

NOTE: The stellar densities may differ somewhat (by up to 10 per cent) from the data in SAG-LL-012, although they are based on the same galactic model. The reason is that the present results used interpolation in tables of dens(I,V-I), rather than directly calculated dens(V,V-I).

Table 1. Results averaged over the stars on the whole sky.

# Sky averages:										
#	V	glat	glon	eclat	area	dens	<V-I>	<G>	<se_par>	<se_pm>
11.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	14.73	.55	10.81	3.96	2.80	
11.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	28.37	.74	11.20	3.95	2.79	
12.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	46.00	.90	11.60	4.01	2.83	
12.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	63.79	.88	12.12	4.56	3.22	
13.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	90.47	.86	12.63	5.36	3.78	
13.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	132.05	.87	13.13	6.41	4.52	
14.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	189.80	.90	13.61	7.76	5.46	
14.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	273.56	.93	14.10	9.52	6.69	
15.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	389.71	.95	14.59	11.78	8.27	
15.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	541.37	.98	15.07	14.68	10.30	
16.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	757.67	1.01	15.56	18.48	12.94	
16.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	1021.51	1.03	16.04	23.45	16.39	
17.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	1412.73	1.06	16.53	30.01	20.96	
17.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	1874.44	1.09	17.01	38.84	27.08	
18.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	2484.87	1.13	17.49	50.89	35.43	
18.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	3308.36	1.17	17.96	67.95	47.22	
19.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	4360.97	1.21	18.43	92.80	64.30	
19.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	5814.11	1.26	18.90	129.77	89.64	
20.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	7563.92	1.32	19.36	184.54	127.11	
20.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	9815.83	1.41	19.81	271.67	186.72	
21.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	12023.70	1.49	20.25	452.70	310.46	
21.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	14277.39	1.62	20.67	911.19	624.25	
22.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	14529.47	1.83	21.02	1959.14	1344.10	
22.50	0	0	.0	41254.0	12485.34	2.20	21.26	3388.09	2339.83	
23.00	0	0	.0	41254.0	11855.06	2.43	21.58	8028.62	5547.83	

Table 2. Results averages over the stars in zones of galactic latitude.

# Averages in zones of galactic latitude:										
#	V	glat	glon	eclat	area	dens	<V-I>	<G>	<se_par>	<se_pm>
11.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	8.64	.58	10.80	4.14	2.61	
11.00	-60	0	-27.5	3651.0	10.57	.59	10.79	4.05	2.84	
11.00	-40	0	-22.7	3836.4	13.70	.61	10.78	4.02	2.92	
11.00	-30	0	-19.3	3093.6	15.69	.62	10.78	3.98	2.83	
11.00	-20	0	-13.6	3340.8	17.39	.57	10.80	3.93	2.76	
11.00	-10	0	-7.1	2599.2	18.43	.47	10.84	3.89	2.74	
11.00	-5	0	-3.8	1485.6	17.70	.44	10.86	3.87	2.75	
11.00	-2	0	-1.7	1238.4	16.07	.45	10.86	3.87	2.75	
11.00	2	0	1.0	1238.4	16.07	.45	10.86	3.87	2.75	

11.00	5	0	3.1	1485.6	17.70	.44	10.86	3.87	2.75
11.00	10	0	6.4	2599.2	18.43	.47	10.84	3.89	2.75
11.00	20	0	12.9	3340.8	17.39	.57	10.80	3.93	2.76
11.00	30	0	18.6	3093.6	15.69	.62	10.78	3.99	2.83
11.00	40	0	22.2	3836.4	13.70	.61	10.78	4.03	2.93
11.00	60	0	27.4	3651.0	10.57	.59	10.79	4.05	2.85
11.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	8.64	.58	10.80	4.14	2.61
11.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	11.16	.63	11.27	4.14	2.61
11.50	-60	0	-27.6	3651.0	14.15	.65	11.25	4.05	2.84
11.50	-40	0	-22.9	3836.4	22.11	.75	11.21	4.02	2.92
11.50	-30	0	-19.4	3093.6	29.17	.81	11.17	3.98	2.83
11.50	-20	0	-13.8	3340.8	38.78	.86	11.15	3.93	2.76
11.50	-10	0	-7.3	2599.2	42.02	.74	11.20	3.89	2.74
11.50	-5	0	-3.9	1485.6	40.22	.62	11.26	3.88	2.75
11.50	-2	0	-1.8	1238.4	35.92	.60	11.28	3.87	2.75
11.50	2	0	.9	1238.4	35.92	.60	11.28	3.87	2.75
11.50	5	0	2.9	1485.6	40.22	.62	11.26	3.88	2.75
11.50	10	0	6.2	2599.2	42.02	.74	11.20	3.89	2.75
11.50	20	0	12.7	3340.8	38.78	.86	11.15	3.94	2.76
11.50	30	0	18.4	3093.6	29.17	.81	11.17	3.99	2.82
11.50	40	0	22.1	3836.4	22.11	.75	11.21	4.03	2.93
11.50	60	0	27.3	3651.0	14.15	.65	11.25	4.06	2.85
11.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	11.16	.63	11.27	4.14	2.61
12.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	13.52	.54	11.82	4.41	2.77
12.00	-60	0	-27.6	3651.0	17.06	.55	11.81	4.30	3.02
12.00	-40	0	-22.9	3836.4	26.56	.66	11.75	4.21	3.06
12.00	-30	0	-19.5	3093.6	37.25	.78	11.68	4.10	2.92
12.00	-20	0	-14.1	3340.8	60.36	.98	11.57	3.95	2.78
12.00	-10	0	-7.6	2599.2	91.21	1.12	11.48	3.89	2.74
12.00	-5	0	-4.1	1485.6	83.92	.94	11.57	3.89	2.76
12.00	-2	0	-2.0	1238.4	70.48	.88	11.62	3.93	2.79
12.00	2	0	.8	1238.4	70.48	.88	11.62	3.93	2.79
12.00	5	0	2.7	1485.6	83.92	.94	11.57	3.90	2.76
12.00	10	0	5.9	2599.2	91.21	1.12	11.48	3.90	2.75
12.00	20	0	12.3	3340.8	60.36	.98	11.57	3.97	2.77
12.00	30	0	18.2	3093.6	37.25	.78	11.68	4.12	2.91
12.00	40	0	22.0	3836.4	26.56	.66	11.75	4.22	3.07
12.00	60	0	27.3	3651.0	17.06	.55	11.81	4.31	3.02
12.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	13.52	.54	11.82	4.41	2.77
12.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	18.52	.53	12.32	5.09	3.20
12.50	-60	0	-27.6	3651.0	23.36	.53	12.32	4.97	3.49
12.50	-40	0	-22.9	3836.4	35.15	.58	12.30	4.91	3.56
12.50	-30	0	-19.5	3093.6	48.01	.65	12.26	4.80	3.41
12.50	-20	0	-14.1	3340.8	75.47	.82	12.16	4.61	3.24
12.50	-10	0	-7.8	2599.2	130.25	1.13	11.96	4.32	3.03
12.50	-5	0	-4.3	1485.6	130.05	1.06	12.00	4.34	3.08
12.50	-2	0	-2.1	1238.4	111.20	.94	12.08	4.43	3.15
12.50	2	0	.6	1238.4	111.20	.94	12.08	4.43	3.15
12.50	5	0	2.5	1485.6	130.05	1.06	12.00	4.34	3.07
12.50	10	0	5.7	2599.2	130.25	1.13	11.96	4.33	3.05
12.50	20	0	12.3	3340.8	75.47	.82	12.16	4.63	3.24
12.50	30	0	18.2	3093.6	48.01	.65	12.26	4.82	3.40
12.50	40	0	22.0	3836.4	35.15	.58	12.30	4.92	3.57
12.50	60	0	27.3	3651.0	23.36	.53	12.32	4.98	3.50
12.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	18.52	.53	12.32	5.09	3.20
13.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	25.68	.55	12.81	5.99	3.77
13.00	-60	0	-27.6	3651.0	32.50	.54	12.82	5.86	4.11
13.00	-40	0	-23.0	3836.4	49.42	.56	12.80	5.81	4.21
13.00	-30	0	-19.5	3093.6	67.74	.62	12.78	5.69	4.04
13.00	-20	0	-14.1	3340.8	105.71	.75	12.70	5.49	3.85
13.00	-10	0	-7.9	2599.2	182.65	1.05	12.52	5.12	3.59
13.00	-5	0	-4.4	1485.6	191.66	1.10	12.47	5.01	3.55
13.00	-2	0	-2.2	1238.4	161.63	1.07	12.50	5.04	3.58

13.00	2	0	.5	1238.4	161.63	1.07	12.50	5.04	3.58
13.00	5	0	2.4	1485.6	191.66	1.10	12.47	5.02	3.55
13.00	10	0	5.5	2599.2	182.65	1.05	12.52	5.14	3.62
13.00	20	0	12.2	3340.8	105.71	.75	12.70	5.51	3.85
13.00	30	0	18.1	3093.6	67.74	.62	12.78	5.71	4.03
13.00	40	0	21.9	3836.4	49.42	.56	12.80	5.82	4.22
13.00	60	0	27.3	3651.0	32.50	.54	12.82	5.87	4.12
13.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	25.68	.55	12.81	5.99	3.77
13.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	34.70	.58	13.30	7.17	4.51
13.50	-60	0	-27.7	3651.0	44.66	.57	13.30	7.02	4.92
13.50	-40	0	-23.0	3836.4	69.12	.58	13.30	6.97	5.06
13.50	-30	0	-19.6	3093.6	95.81	.61	13.28	6.86	4.87
13.50	-20	0	-14.2	3340.8	151.44	.72	13.22	6.64	4.65
13.50	-10	0	-8.1	2599.2	275.76	1.04	13.03	6.12	4.29
13.50	-5	0	-4.5	1485.6	288.76	1.13	12.96	5.94	4.20
13.50	-2	0	-2.3	1238.4	241.84	1.05	13.01	6.04	4.29
13.50	2	0	.4	1238.4	241.84	1.05	13.01	6.04	4.28
13.50	5	0	2.2	1485.6	288.76	1.13	12.96	5.94	4.20
13.50	10	0	5.3	2599.2	275.76	1.04	13.03	6.15	4.32
13.50	20	0	12.0	3340.8	151.44	.72	13.22	6.67	4.65
13.50	30	0	18.0	3093.6	95.81	.61	13.28	6.89	4.86
13.50	40	0	21.8	3836.4	69.12	.58	13.30	7.00	5.07
13.50	60	0	27.2	3651.0	44.66	.57	13.30	7.03	4.94
13.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	34.70	.58	13.30	7.17	4.51
14.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	46.40	.62	13.78	8.69	5.47
14.00	-60	0	-27.7	3651.0	60.24	.60	13.79	8.52	5.98
14.00	-40	0	-23.0	3836.4	95.52	.60	13.79	8.49	6.15
14.00	-30	0	-19.6	3093.6	134.37	.62	13.78	8.37	5.94
14.00	-20	0	-14.2	3340.8	214.78	.70	13.74	8.14	5.71
14.00	-10	0	-8.2	2599.2	408.83	1.04	13.54	7.48	5.23
14.00	-5	0	-4.7	1485.6	441.30	1.21	13.42	7.08	5.00
14.00	-2	0	-2.3	1238.4	333.59	1.13	13.47	7.19	5.10
14.00	2	0	.4	1238.4	333.59	1.13	13.47	7.19	5.10
14.00	5	0	2.0	1485.6	441.30	1.21	13.42	7.09	4.99
14.00	10	0	5.0	2599.2	408.83	1.04	13.54	7.51	5.27
14.00	20	0	11.9	3340.8	214.78	.70	13.74	8.18	5.70
14.00	30	0	17.9	3093.6	134.37	.62	13.78	8.42	5.93
14.00	40	0	21.7	3836.4	95.52	.60	13.79	8.52	6.17
14.00	60	0	27.2	3651.0	60.24	.60	13.79	8.54	6.00
14.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	46.40	.62	13.78	8.69	5.47
14.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	59.72	.66	14.26	10.65	6.70
14.50	-60	0	-27.7	3651.0	79.22	.64	14.27	10.45	7.33
14.50	-40	0	-23.1	3836.4	129.67	.62	14.28	10.44	7.57
14.50	-30	0	-19.7	3093.6	185.97	.63	14.27	10.32	7.33
14.50	-20	0	-14.3	3340.8	301.33	.69	14.24	10.10	7.08
14.50	-10	0	-8.3	2599.2	596.48	1.01	14.06	9.29	6.48
14.50	-5	0	-4.9	1485.6	672.87	1.28	13.87	8.54	6.02
14.50	-2	0	-2.5	1238.4	518.03	1.18	13.95	8.76	6.21
14.50	2	0	.2	1238.4	518.03	1.18	13.95	8.76	6.20
14.50	5	0	1.8	1485.6	672.87	1.28	13.87	8.56	6.02
14.50	10	0	4.8	2599.2	596.48	1.01	14.06	9.34	6.54
14.50	20	0	11.8	3340.8	301.33	.69	14.24	10.15	7.07
14.50	30	0	17.8	3093.6	185.97	.63	14.27	10.39	7.31
14.50	40	0	21.6	3836.4	129.67	.62	14.28	10.49	7.59
14.50	60	0	27.2	3651.0	79.22	.64	14.27	10.48	7.36
14.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	59.72	.66	14.26	10.65	6.70
15.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	75.28	.70	14.73	13.14	8.26
15.00	-60	0	-27.7	3651.0	101.17	.67	14.75	12.93	9.07
15.00	-40	0	-23.2	3836.4	172.63	.65	14.76	12.95	9.38
15.00	-30	0	-19.7	3093.6	253.85	.65	14.76	12.83	9.11
15.00	-20	0	-14.4	3340.8	421.25	.69	14.75	12.63	8.84
15.00	-10	0	-8.4	2599.2	854.89	.98	14.58	11.70	8.15
15.00	-5	0	-5.1	1485.6	1039.57	1.35	14.34	10.46	7.35

15.00	-2	0	-2.6	1238.4	762.07	1.23	14.42	10.72	7.59
15.00	2	0	.1	1238.4	762.07	1.23	14.42	10.73	7.59
15.00	5	0	1.5	1485.6	1039.57	1.35	14.34	10.48	7.35
15.00	10	0	4.7	2599.2	854.89	.98	14.58	11.76	8.23
15.00	20	0	11.7	3340.8	421.25	.69	14.75	12.70	8.84
15.00	30	0	17.6	3093.6	253.85	.65	14.76	12.92	9.08
15.00	40	0	21.5	3836.4	172.63	.65	14.76	13.01	9.42
15.00	60	0	27.1	3651.0	101.17	.67	14.75	12.97	9.10
15.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	75.28	.70	14.73	13.14	8.26
15.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	92.90	.75	15.20	16.30	10.25
15.50	-60	0	-27.8	3651.0	126.81	.72	15.22	16.07	11.26
15.50	-40	0	-23.2	3836.4	224.91	.69	15.24	16.15	11.70
15.50	-30	0	-19.8	3093.6	340.09	.68	15.25	16.05	11.39
15.50	-20	0	-14.4	3340.8	584.03	.69	15.24	15.88	11.12
15.50	-10	0	-8.5	2599.2	1204.42	.94	15.11	14.88	10.36
15.50	-5	0	-5.4	1485.6	1599.67	1.39	14.81	12.97	9.09
15.50	-2	0	-2.7	1238.4	970.92	1.37	14.83	12.90	9.13
15.50	2	0	.0	1238.4	970.92	1.37	14.83	12.91	9.13
15.50	5	0	1.2	1485.6	1599.67	1.39	14.81	13.00	9.09
15.50	10	0	4.6	2599.2	1204.42	.94	15.11	14.97	10.47
15.50	20	0	11.5	3340.8	584.03	.69	15.24	15.97	11.11
15.50	30	0	17.5	3093.6	340.09	.68	15.25	16.17	11.35
15.50	40	0	21.4	3836.4	224.91	.69	15.24	16.24	11.74
15.50	60	0	27.1	3651.0	126.81	.72	15.22	16.13	11.31
15.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	92.90	.75	15.20	16.30	10.25
16.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	113.08	.80	15.67	20.32	12.79
16.00	-60	0	-27.8	3651.0	156.01	.77	15.69	20.06	14.06
16.00	-40	0	-23.3	3836.4	286.39	.73	15.72	20.27	14.66
16.00	-30	0	-19.9	3093.6	448.02	.71	15.73	20.20	14.33
16.00	-20	0	-14.5	3340.8	801.04	.71	15.74	20.08	14.05
16.00	-10	0	-8.6	2599.2	1686.24	.90	15.64	19.07	13.26
16.00	-5	0	-5.6	1485.6	2377.78	1.41	15.30	16.34	11.42
16.00	-2	0	-2.8	1238.4	1474.78	1.40	15.31	16.12	11.39
16.00	2	0	-.2	1238.4	1474.78	1.40	15.31	16.12	11.38
16.00	5	0	.9	1485.6	2377.78	1.41	15.30	16.38	11.42
16.00	10	0	4.5	2599.2	1686.24	.90	15.64	19.19	13.41
16.00	20	0	11.3	3340.8	801.04	.71	15.74	20.21	14.04
16.00	30	0	17.3	3093.6	448.02	.71	15.73	20.36	14.27
16.00	40	0	21.3	3836.4	286.39	.73	15.72	20.39	14.73
16.00	60	0	27.1	3651.0	156.01	.77	15.69	20.14	14.13
16.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	113.08	.80	15.67	20.32	12.79
16.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	136.62	.86	16.13	25.47	16.02
16.50	-60	0	-27.8	3651.0	189.23	.82	16.16	25.19	17.65
16.50	-40	0	-23.4	3836.4	356.43	.77	16.20	25.58	18.49
16.50	-30	0	-19.9	3093.6	574.71	.75	16.21	25.56	18.13
16.50	-20	0	-14.6	3340.8	1077.84	.73	16.22	25.54	17.86
16.50	-10	0	-8.7	2599.2	2356.92	.87	16.15	24.62	17.10
16.50	-5	0	-5.8	1485.6	3425.90	1.41	15.81	20.90	14.57
16.50	-2	0	-3.0	1238.4	1800.07	1.55	15.71	19.51	13.77
16.50	2	0	-.3	1238.4	1800.07	1.55	15.71	19.53	13.76
16.50	5	0	.7	1485.6	3425.90	1.41	15.81	20.96	14.57
16.50	10	0	4.3	2599.2	2356.92	.87	16.15	24.77	17.30
16.50	20	0	11.1	3340.8	1077.84	.73	16.22	25.73	17.85
16.50	30	0	17.1	3093.6	574.71	.75	16.21	25.79	18.06
16.50	40	0	21.1	3836.4	356.43	.77	16.20	25.75	18.59
16.50	60	0	27.0	3651.0	189.23	.82	16.16	25.31	17.75
16.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	136.62	.86	16.13	25.47	16.02
17.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	164.32	.92	16.59	32.18	20.24
17.00	-60	0	-27.9	3651.0	228.29	.88	16.62	31.92	22.36
17.00	-40	0	-23.5	3836.4	435.27	.82	16.66	32.54	23.50
17.00	-30	0	-20.0	3093.6	715.49	.79	16.69	32.60	23.11
17.00	-20	0	-14.7	3340.8	1397.52	.77	16.70	32.68	22.85
17.00	-10	0	-8.8	2599.2	3313.61	.86	16.66	31.97	22.17

17.00	-5	0	-5.9	1485.6	4853.84	1.37	16.34	27.26	18.96
17.00	-2	0	-3.1	1238.4	2991.05	1.58	16.19	24.78	17.47
17.00	2	0	-.5	1238.4	2991.05	1.58	16.19	24.80	17.46
17.00	5	0	.5	1485.6	4853.84	1.37	16.34	27.33	18.96
17.00	10	0	4.2	2599.2	3313.61	.86	16.66	32.18	22.44
17.00	20	0	11.0	3340.8	1397.52	.77	16.70	32.94	22.83
17.00	30	0	16.9	3093.6	715.49	.79	16.69	32.92	23.01
17.00	40	0	21.0	3836.4	435.27	.82	16.66	32.77	23.63
17.00	60	0	26.9	3651.0	228.29	.88	16.62	32.09	22.49
17.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	164.32	.92	16.59	32.18	20.24
17.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	198.14	.98	17.05	41.08	25.85
17.50	-60	0	-27.9	3651.0	276.17	.93	17.08	40.83	28.58
17.50	-40	0	-23.5	3836.4	528.93	.87	17.13	41.86	30.19
17.50	-30	0	-20.1	3093.6	881.20	.84	17.16	42.05	29.79
17.50	-20	0	-14.8	3340.8	1788.07	.82	17.18	42.29	29.55
17.50	-10	0	-8.8	2599.2	4439.30	.88	17.15	41.58	28.82
17.50	-5	0	-6.0	1485.6	6814.09	1.32	16.88	36.21	25.14
17.50	-2	0	-3.3	1238.4	4030.60	1.67	16.62	30.97	21.79
17.50	2	0	-.7	1238.4	4030.60	1.67	16.62	31.00	21.78
17.50	5	0	.3	1485.6	6814.09	1.32	16.88	36.31	25.15
17.50	10	0	4.1	2599.2	4439.30	.88	17.15	41.86	29.20
17.50	20	0	10.8	3340.8	1788.07	.82	17.18	42.66	29.52
17.50	30	0	16.7	3093.6	881.20	.84	17.16	42.51	29.65
17.50	40	0	20.8	3836.4	528.93	.87	17.13	42.20	30.39
17.50	60	0	26.9	3651.0	276.17	.93	17.08	41.07	28.78
17.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	198.14	.98	17.05	41.08	25.85
18.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	238.40	1.05	17.51	53.14	33.43
18.00	-60	0	-28.0	3651.0	333.96	.99	17.54	53.02	37.09
18.00	-40	0	-23.6	3836.4	646.82	.91	17.60	54.81	39.43
18.00	-30	0	-20.2	3093.6	1083.23	.88	17.63	55.24	39.08
18.00	-20	0	-14.9	3340.8	2260.99	.86	17.65	55.79	38.92
18.00	-10	0	-9.0	2599.2	6036.54	.92	17.63	54.86	37.98
18.00	-5	0	-6.1	1485.6	9314.42	1.28	17.41	48.64	33.75
18.00	-2	0	-3.5	1238.4	5485.32	1.83	17.01	38.34	26.90
18.00	2	0	-.9	1238.4	5485.32	1.83	17.01	38.38	26.89
18.00	5	0	.3	1485.6	9314.42	1.28	17.41	48.79	33.77
18.00	10	0	3.9	2599.2	6036.54	.92	17.63	55.26	38.51
18.00	20	0	10.5	3340.8	2260.99	.86	17.65	56.32	38.89
18.00	30	0	16.3	3093.6	1083.23	.88	17.63	55.93	38.88
18.00	40	0	20.5	3836.4	646.82	.91	17.60	55.31	39.73
18.00	60	0	26.8	3651.0	333.96	.99	17.54	53.37	37.38
18.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	238.40	1.05	17.51	53.14	33.43
18.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	285.82	1.11	17.96	69.83	43.93
18.50	-60	0	-28.0	3651.0	402.90	1.05	18.00	69.98	48.91
18.50	-40	0	-23.7	3836.4	794.95	.96	18.07	73.19	52.49
18.50	-30	0	-20.2	3093.6	1336.03	.92	18.10	74.13	52.32
18.50	-20	0	-15.0	3340.8	2846.69	.89	18.13	75.30	52.38
18.50	-10	0	-9.1	2599.2	8195.89	.95	18.11	74.15	51.18
18.50	-5	0	-6.1	1485.6	12560.83	1.27	17.92	65.98	45.79
18.50	-2	0	-3.7	1238.4	7848.21	1.91	17.45	49.15	34.40
18.50	2	0	-1.1	1238.4	7848.21	1.91	17.45	49.20	34.38
18.50	5	0	.3	1485.6	12560.83	1.27	17.92	66.18	45.81
18.50	10	0	3.7	2599.2	8195.89	.95	18.11	74.74	51.96
18.50	20	0	10.0	3340.8	2846.69	.89	18.13	76.11	52.40
18.50	30	0	15.9	3093.6	1336.03	.92	18.10	75.17	52.07
18.50	40	0	20.2	3836.4	794.95	.96	18.07	73.95	52.98
18.50	60	0	26.7	3651.0	402.90	1.05	18.00	70.48	49.33
18.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	285.82	1.11	17.96	69.83	43.93
19.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	339.96	1.19	18.41	93.43	58.78
19.00	-60	0	-28.0	3651.0	481.84	1.12	18.45	94.01	65.67
19.00	-40	0	-23.7	3836.4	970.36	1.01	18.53	99.71	71.29
19.00	-30	0	-20.3	3093.6	1641.40	.96	18.57	101.62	71.55
19.00	-20	0	-15.1	3340.8	3537.49	.92	18.61	104.23	72.27

19.00	-10	0	-9.3	2599.2	11082.03	.98	18.60	102.93	70.76
19.00	-5	0	-6.2	1485.6	17140.79	1.27	18.43	91.78	63.62
19.00	-2	0	-4.0	1238.4	10366.16	2.06	17.83	62.20	43.37
19.00	2	0	-1.4	1238.4	10366.16	2.06	17.83	62.26	43.35
19.00	5	0	.1	1485.6	17140.79	1.27	18.43	92.07	63.64
19.00	10	0	3.3	2599.2	11082.03	.98	18.60	103.83	71.91
19.00	20	0	9.6	3340.8	3537.49	.92	18.61	105.50	72.40
19.00	30	0	15.6	3093.6	1641.40	.96	18.57	103.18	71.22
19.00	40	0	20.0	3836.4	970.36	1.01	18.53	100.85	72.06
19.00	60	0	26.7	3651.0	481.84	1.12	18.45	94.73	66.28
19.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	339.96	1.19	18.41	93.43	58.78
19.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	399.72	1.27	18.85	127.43	80.17
19.50	-60	0	-28.1	3651.0	567.79	1.20	18.90	128.48	89.71
19.50	-40	0	-23.7	3836.4	1160.87	1.07	18.98	137.95	98.43
19.50	-30	0	-20.3	3093.6	1973.35	1.02	19.03	141.40	99.37
19.50	-20	0	-15.2	3340.8	4288.80	.96	19.07	146.63	101.40
19.50	-10	0	-9.5	2599.2	14812.25	.99	19.08	147.48	100.94
19.50	-5	0	-6.4	1485.6	23909.73	1.27	18.93	130.55	90.28
19.50	-2	0	-4.1	1238.4	14854.24	2.12	18.29	83.60	58.17
19.50	2	0	-1.6	1238.4	14854.24	2.12	18.29	83.70	58.14
19.50	5	0	-.1	1485.6	23909.73	1.27	18.93	130.99	90.33
19.50	10	0	2.9	2599.2	14812.25	.99	19.08	148.89	102.68
19.50	20	0	9.3	3340.8	4288.80	.96	19.07	148.56	101.69
19.50	30	0	15.3	3093.6	1973.35	1.02	19.03	143.70	98.95
19.50	40	0	19.8	3836.4	1160.87	1.07	18.98	139.63	99.59
19.50	60	0	26.6	3651.0	567.79	1.20	18.90	129.48	90.57
19.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	399.72	1.27	18.85	127.43	80.17
20.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	463.24	1.35	19.30	177.26	111.52
20.00	-60	0	-28.1	3651.0	657.81	1.30	19.33	178.73	124.80
20.00	-40	0	-23.7	3836.4	1345.94	1.17	19.42	192.89	137.58
20.00	-30	0	-20.3	3093.6	2292.34	1.12	19.46	198.50	139.42
20.00	-20	0	-15.2	3340.8	4996.87	1.05	19.52	207.98	143.63
20.00	-10	0	-9.6	2599.2	18666.63	1.03	19.56	215.93	147.25
20.00	-5	0	-6.5	1485.6	33600.44	1.30	19.41	190.12	131.06
20.00	-2	0	-4.3	1238.4	20668.11	2.19	18.74	114.07	79.09
20.00	2	0	-1.8	1238.4	20668.11	2.19	18.74	114.21	79.07
20.00	5	0	-.3	1485.6	33600.44	1.30	19.41	190.81	131.17
20.00	10	0	2.6	2599.2	18666.63	1.03	19.56	218.12	149.89
20.00	20	0	9.1	3340.8	4996.87	1.05	19.52	210.82	144.13
20.00	30	0	15.2	3093.6	2292.34	1.12	19.46	201.79	138.84
20.00	40	0	19.8	3836.4	1345.94	1.17	19.42	195.26	139.23
20.00	60	0	26.6	3651.0	657.81	1.30	19.33	180.12	125.99
20.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	463.24	1.35	19.30	177.26	111.52
20.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	528.30	1.45	19.73	253.79	159.66
20.50	-60	0	-28.1	3651.0	748.95	1.40	19.77	255.85	178.69
20.50	-40	0	-23.7	3836.4	1523.13	1.30	19.84	277.36	197.97
20.50	-30	0	-20.3	3093.6	2591.21	1.25	19.88	286.72	201.44
20.50	-20	0	-15.2	3340.8	5644.73	1.18	19.94	304.52	210.24
20.50	-10	0	-9.7	2599.2	22294.57	1.10	20.02	329.27	224.03
20.50	-5	0	-6.7	1485.6	47466.95	1.32	19.89	289.99	199.12
20.50	-2	0	-4.5	1238.4	30542.73	2.21	19.23	164.63	113.95
20.50	2	0	-2.0	1238.4	30542.73	2.21	19.23	164.85	113.92
20.50	5	0	-.6	1485.6	47466.95	1.32	19.89	291.14	199.38
20.50	10	0	2.4	2599.2	22294.57	1.10	20.02	332.72	228.14
20.50	20	0	9.1	3340.8	5644.73	1.18	19.94	308.70	211.00
20.50	30	0	15.3	3093.6	2591.21	1.25	19.88	291.43	200.60
20.50	40	0	19.8	3836.4	1523.13	1.30	19.84	280.68	200.27
20.50	60	0	26.7	3651.0	748.95	1.40	19.77	257.82	180.37
20.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	528.30	1.45	19.73	253.79	159.66
21.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	594.74	1.54	20.17	391.49	246.29
21.00	-60	0	-28.0	3651.0	842.23	1.51	20.19	397.00	277.35
21.00	-40	0	-23.7	3836.4	1702.43	1.43	20.25	438.38	313.23
21.00	-30	0	-20.2	3093.6	2887.75	1.40	20.29	457.03	321.31

21.00	-20	0	-15.2	3340.8	6274.05	1.33	20.34	495.90	342.53
21.00	-10	0	-9.7	2599.2	25198.23	1.20	20.45	580.07	394.25
21.00	-5	0	-6.9	1485.6	64656.27	1.35	20.37	511.82	350.09
21.00	-2	0	-4.6	1238.4	37259.55	2.29	19.67	235.63	162.67
21.00	2	0	-2.1	1238.4	37259.55	2.29	19.67	235.96	162.64
21.00	5	0	-0.9	1485.6	64656.27	1.35	20.37	513.98	350.71
21.00	10	0	2.3	2599.2	25198.23	1.20	20.45	586.22	401.51
21.00	20	0	9.2	3340.8	6274.05	1.33	20.34	502.60	343.71
21.00	30	0	15.4	3093.6	2887.75	1.40	20.29	464.34	319.95
21.00	40	0	19.9	3836.4	1702.43	1.43	20.25	443.47	316.71
21.00	60	0	26.7	3651.0	842.23	1.51	20.19	399.98	279.89
21.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	594.74	1.54	20.17	391.49	246.29
21.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	553.08	1.89	20.45	577.09	363.05
21.50	-60	0	-28.0	3651.0	795.65	1.85	20.48	598.60	418.34
21.50	-40	0	-23.6	3836.4	1683.52	1.73	20.57	718.61	513.97
21.50	-30	0	-20.2	3093.6	2938.20	1.67	20.62	784.43	551.99
21.50	-20	0	-15.1	3340.8	6594.45	1.56	20.70	922.11	637.68
21.50	-10	0	-9.7	2599.2	26934.00	1.36	20.85	1272.62	865.32
21.50	-5	0	-7.0	1485.6	80869.59	1.42	20.83	1210.09	825.74
21.50	-2	0	-4.7	1238.4	50956.56	2.30	20.17	385.99	266.10
21.50	2	0	-2.2	1238.4	50956.56	2.30	20.17	386.55	266.05
21.50	5	0	-1.0	1485.6	80869.59	1.42	20.83	1215.44	827.48
21.50	10	0	2.3	2599.2	26934.00	1.36	20.85	1286.06	881.23
21.50	20	0	9.3	3340.8	6594.45	1.56	20.70	934.02	639.64
21.50	30	0	15.6	3093.6	2938.20	1.67	20.62	796.22	549.78
21.50	40	0	20.1	3836.4	1683.52	1.73	20.57	726.48	519.38
21.50	60	0	26.7	3651.0	795.65	1.85	20.48	602.78	421.91
21.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	553.08	1.89	20.45	577.09	363.05
22.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	492.10	2.24	20.70	917.44	577.17
22.00	-60	0	-27.9	3651.0	708.47	2.22	20.73	939.80	657.99
22.00	-40	0	-23.5	3836.4	1437.08	2.17	20.76	1026.64	740.71
22.00	-30	0	-20.1	3093.6	2475.75	2.14	20.80	1087.56	770.42
22.00	-20	0	-14.9	3340.8	5349.19	2.06	20.86	1247.49	870.31
22.00	-10	0	-9.4	2599.2	20394.88	1.79	21.06	2061.38	1413.95
22.00	-5	0	-7.1	1485.6	92444.80	1.52	21.26	3526.21	2404.24
22.00	-2	0	-4.8	1238.4	60597.14	2.32	20.65	817.19	562.29
22.00	2	0	-2.4	1238.4	60597.14	2.32	20.65	818.42	562.24
22.00	5	0	-1.1	1485.6	92444.80	1.52	21.26	3542.06	2409.52
22.00	10	0	3.1	2599.2	20394.88	1.79	21.06	2080.20	1437.51
22.00	20	0	10.5	3340.8	5349.19	2.06	20.86	1259.15	869.87
22.00	30	0	16.7	3093.6	2475.75	2.14	20.80	1099.48	766.75
22.00	40	0	20.9	3836.4	1437.08	2.17	20.76	1034.50	745.31
22.00	60	0	26.9	3651.0	708.47	2.22	20.73	945.01	662.32
22.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	492.10	2.24	20.70	917.44	577.17
22.50	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	468.52	2.43	21.06	2076.66	1306.44
22.50	-60	0	-27.9	3651.0	676.80	2.42	21.07	2082.54	1459.52
22.50	-40	0	-23.4	3836.4	1384.82	2.41	21.08	2155.58	1560.83
22.50	-30	0	-20.0	3093.6	2425.18	2.39	21.10	2245.10	1594.79
22.50	-20	0	-14.8	3340.8	5374.29	2.32	21.16	2600.53	1820.41
22.50	-10	0	-9.1	2599.2	18268.87	2.13	21.31	3845.30	2655.80
22.50	-5	0	-6.4	1485.6	44857.43	1.93	21.46	5854.70	4045.31
22.50	-2	0	-4.9	1238.4	88438.45	2.34	21.14	2547.76	1750.52
22.50	2	0	-2.5	1238.4	88438.45	2.34	21.14	2551.73	1750.43
22.50	5	0	-0.1	1485.6	44857.43	1.93	21.46	5875.06	4047.47
22.50	10	0	3.7	2599.2	18268.87	2.13	21.31	3875.99	2696.26
22.50	20	0	11.0	3340.8	5374.29	2.32	21.16	2621.08	1817.17
22.50	30	0	17.2	3093.6	2425.18	2.39	21.10	2265.55	1587.07
22.50	40	0	21.2	3836.4	1384.82	2.41	21.08	2168.98	1567.76
22.50	60	0	27.0	3651.0	676.80	2.42	21.07	2092.54	1467.66
22.50	90	0	29.8	1382.0	468.52	2.43	21.06	2076.66	1306.44
23.00	-90	0	-29.8	1382.0	348.28	2.74	21.31	3971.50	2498.50
23.00	-60	0	-27.8	3651.0	513.37	2.72	21.32	4002.08	2807.80
23.00	-40	0	-23.3	3836.4	1140.11	2.68	21.36	4390.09	3186.19

23.00	-30	0	-19.9	3093.6	2136.54	2.64	21.40	4816.62	3425.88
23.00	-20	0	-14.6	3340.8	4955.91	2.56	21.46	5711.35	4006.65
23.00	-10	0	-8.7	2599.2	13587.25	2.52	21.50	6379.98	4444.08
23.00	-5	0	-5.5	1485.6	20233.75	2.52	21.50	6340.93	4445.41
23.00	-2	0	-5.1	1238.4	120529.10	2.35	21.64	9695.42	6646.59
23.00	2	0	-2.6	1238.4	120529.10	2.35	21.64	9711.19	6646.94
23.00	5	0	1.0	1485.6	20233.75	2.52	21.50	6354.79	4442.31
23.00	10	0	4.5	2599.2	13587.25	2.52	21.50	6418.63	4497.65
23.00	20	0	11.4	3340.8	4955.91	2.56	21.46	5748.93	3997.71
23.00	30	0	17.6	3093.6	2136.54	2.64	21.40	4852.67	3410.98
23.00	40	0	21.5	3836.4	1140.11	2.68	21.36	4411.14	3196.09
23.00	60	0	27.1	3651.0	513.37	2.72	21.32	4016.13	2819.02
23.00	90	0	29.8	1382.0	348.28	2.74	21.31	3971.50	2498.50

Table 3. Results in various galactic directions, averaged over colour.
(The complete file is sag_ll_023_tab3.txt, about 400 kbytes.)

# Local averages:										
#	V	glat	glon	eclat	area	dens	<V-I>	<G>	<se_par>	<se_pm>
11.00	-90	0		-29.8	1382.0	8.64	.58	10.80	4.14	2.61
11.00	-60	0		-28.6	608.5	11.22	.59	10.79	4.19	2.66
.....										
23.00	60	300		1.9	608.5	559.40	2.71	21.33	4639.92	3094.58
23.00	90	0		29.8	1382.0	348.28	2.74	21.31	3971.50	2498.50
